

Challenges and Risks for Higher Education Now and Beyond the 2030

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Abstract

The role of higher education is very crucial in our education system for sustainable development. The aim and objectives of the research was to explore challenges and risks for higher education now and beyond the 2030. What would measure higher education should take for future modern challenges. The study was qualitative in nature and interviews based. 36-degree awarding institutes were chosen randomly then 144 faculty members were select for sample. It was found that due to high fesses dropout rate is high, public-private partnership is weak, curriculum is not reviewed from many years. Institutions has political influences and has no autonomy. It is recommended that government enhance higher education budget to lowers the fesses. Research and development should be enhancing. Education should be practical and according to the need of market.

Keywords: challenges and risks, higher education, now and beyond 2030, challenges for HEC.

Introduction

Higher education is the third and final level after high school. It typically consists of undergraduate and graduate studies at colleges and universities. Higher education allows you to study a topic in which you are interested, and it can also improve your career prospects and earning potential (2 citation). The Framework for Higher Education Qualifications (FHEQ) provides detailed descriptions of the most important higher education credentials.

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Most higher education qualifications correspond to levels 4 through 8 of the FHEQ. Higher National Certificates (HNC) and Higher National Diplomas (HND), Foundation degree course certificates, and other academic awards granted by a university or higher education college are the primary qualifications. Other qualifications include postgraduate qualifications, bachelor's degrees, higher national certificates and diplomas, and foundation degree course certificates (Nidirect, 2022).

It's possible that academic credentials aren't necessary to enter a higher education institution. There are a few educational institutions that are open to the idea of accepting jobs and life experience in place of formal education. If you seek to attend an Access course, a Foundation course, or a Foundation year, your previous work experience could also be considered. On the other hand, it is not very common in Pakistan. Higher education may be understood as "any sort of education delivered at post-secondary institutions of learning, generally after a term of study, a degree, diploma, or certificate of higher education," according to one definition. Schools that prepare students to become teachers, as well as junior colleges and institutes of technology, are all examples of higher education. Higher education institutions include universities and colleges and a wide variety of vocational schools that teach subjects such as law, theology, medicine, commerce, music, and art. In addition, higher education includes junior colleges, the Institute of Technology, and schools that prepare future teachers (Kaneko, 2019).

In this day and age of advanced technology, archaic practices and antiquated educational programs are still widely used. The traditional instruction technique, which consists of lecturing students, is by no means becoming obsolete soon. Students will be less active as a result of these tactics. Even at the world's most prestigious educational institutions, students must learn content based on antiquated theories and practices. Professors and lecturers deliver classroom lectures from prestigious institutions such as the University of Engineering and Technology (UET) Lahore, the Aga Khan Medical University (AKU) Karachi, and the University of Health Sciences (UHS) Lahore. Students at Harvard, Stanford, and Wharton universities are actively engaged in the study of project-based problem-solving on their respective campuses (Wingard & Farrugia, 2021).

Higher education is an absolute need for the young people of Pakistan, given the country's rapidly expanding population. The younger generation enthusiastically pursues superior education from the most prestigious universities to gain endorsement from large organizations. However, the glass is still just half full, as is customary. The higher education system in Pakistan is plagued by several problems, including insufficient funding for affiliated programs and bureaucratic "red tape." This is further complicated by the conventional educational practices that are used and the expensive tuition that the colleges require. In addition to the low percentage of GDP invested in higher education, there is also a mismatch between the degrees earned and the skills required by the sector. It is still feasible to bring about the essential change, even though these problems affect our nation's higher education system. To revitalize Pakistan's higher education system, there has to be a significant investment made in research and development. In addition, the decrease in prices charged by corporations is considerable. Investing money in cutting-edge technology rather than traditional "brick and mortar" businesses will provide a higher return. Reforming the relevant institutions is very necessary for this respect. Instead of the objective of obtaining a

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job and competing in the rat race, the purpose of our educational system should be to foster the development of businesspeople, innovators, scientists, thinkers, and writers. It is via the implementation of the policy framework that the change will be brought about (Torche, 2019).

Literature Review

It is disheartening to see Pakistan's higher education system in the situation that it is in right now. The system is plagued with a great number of flaws. The growing expense of a well-rounded education compared to the advantages of having a college degree is the most significant flaw in the system. People are required to shoulder the burden of the relevance of universities, regardless of how significant the value of a university education may be. Even though having a college degree is often necessary to succeed in the working world, many people find it impossible to afford the higher education they need. The issue may grow more serious if the expense of higher education rises over what is considered affordable by those in the middle class. Irrational financial solutions have been proposed for students who are now trapped, which makes the issue much worse. Students rarely have the option to take courses online, so they must pay for on-campus housing, food plans, and other related expenses. Continued privatization of public institutions is a major barrier to affordability in higher education for individuals who demonstrate exceptional merit. This directly impacts the nation's growth and prosperity (Khan et al., 2018).

Even enrolling a kid in a public institution may be a difficult financial proposition for many parents today, making it difficult for them to provide for their child's further education. Within this situation, the privatization of education is like pouring salt on an open wound. Because there is insufficient money for higher education institutions provided by the government, universities must go to private sources for their financial support. Consequently, educational institutions have begun to finance their student bodies via a mix of student tuition and various commercial activity (Zaloom, 2019).

In this day and age of advanced technology, archaic practices and antiquated educational programs are still widely used. The traditional instruction technique, which consists of lecturing students, is by no means becoming obsolete soon. Students will be less active as a result of these tactics. Even at the world's most prestigious educational institutions, students must learn content based on antiquated theories and practices. Professors and lecturers deliver classroom lectures from prestigious institutions such as the University of Engineering and Technology (UET) Lahore, the Aga Khan Medical University (AKU) Karachi, and the University of Health Sciences (UHS) Lahore. Students at Harvard, Stanford, and Wharton universities are actively engaged in the study of project-based problem-solving on their respective campuses (Wingard, 2022).

A sickness afflicting our higher education system in Pakistan prevents it from recognizing high-quality faculty members. The quality of the faculty is necessary for the quality of education and research. It is impossible to provide a high-quality education if the teaching staff is not up to the task. Our higher education system suffers from a significant lack of notable professors and lecturers of all levels. Similarly, universities in Pakistan do not have enough qualified faculty members, resulting in a research shortage. The fact that our nation has not produced a single "genuine thinker" in the seventy-two years since it was founded in

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1947 is the most overwhelming indication that this is the case. In addition, there is a scarcity of high-quality instructors, which has resulted in our institutions not having enough people with PhDs. As a result, it is anticipated that the country will participate in fundamental and applied research at Pakistani institutions to reduce the challenges faced by higher education (Farrukh et al., 2019).

The fact that our system is in such precarious shape is reflected in the fact that there is not a significant commitment to research and the production of new knowledge.

The presence of research-related institutions that generate new information is an essential component in the process of knowledge generation. The capacity of an institution to successfully recruit and retain high-performing researchers is critical to its overall output level. There are several instances in our nation that serve to illustrate how complicated our system of higher education can be. The challenges facing Pakistan's higher education system are made worse because institutions aren't given enough attention to innovating. Innovation is lacking in our system of higher education. Our educational institutions struggle to provide students with a high-quality scientific education, which can be seen in several ways (Mendoza & Sanchez, 2018).

Regarding creativity, there is little room for doubt that Pakistan is far behind the rest of the globe. The Global Innovation Index places Pakistan at position 107 out of 141 nations, a disappointing result (GII). It stokes the flames of economic expansion and expansion as a whole. In a similar vein, the incorrect policy of the HEC places a focus only on quantity, with little to no attention, if any, placed on quality. This is because our higher education system is deficient in originality and innovation. It is essential to remember that not a single Pakistani research publication in engineering has been given exposure internationally, nor has it affected the scientific community. The low percentage of GDP invested in excessive higher education levels is a dilemma for our education system (Jalil, 2019).

The aftermath of this sickness acts as a roadblock to the nation's progress toward its full potential. Because education and economic growth are directly related to one another, it is impossible to envision a prosperous future for a nation if that nation does not invest in its educational system. The government has not placed a high priority on the education sector, making it one of the least prioritized areas. This lends credence to the widespread belief that education is not a high priority in Pakistan. Therefore, to debunk the concept described above, Pakistan shall be required to pay attention and take cautious steps regarding the growth of higher education to achieve the greatest number of positive and fruitful results (Tunio et al., 2021).

Present Study

The role of higher education is very crucial in our education system for sustainable development. With time everything is changing, education is also changing; the world is progressing in modern technology and education. The study aimed to explore risks and challenges existing and beyond 2030. What would measure higher education should take for future modern challenges.

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Objectives of Study

The following were the objectives of the study;

1. To explore major issues and challenges facing higher education in Pakistan and what would be beyond 2030.
2. Which steps should higher education in Pakistan take to meet future risks and challenges?
3. To meet future challenges, which initiatives should be taken in social, technological, vernacular, and science subjects?

Research Questions

1. What are the major issues and challenges facing higher education in Pakistan, and what will be beyond 2030?
2. Which steps should higher education in Pakistan take to meet future risks and challenges?
3. To meet future challenges, which initiatives should be taken in social, technological, vernacular, and science subjects?

Methods and Procedures

The study was exploratory; the interview was conducted in four fields, Education, English, Physics, and Chemistry. Data were collected from faculty members of concerned departments.

All the faculty members of Affiliated colleges and universities from HCE were the populations of said research work. There are 2389 colleges and universities affiliated with HEC in four provinces of Pakistan, i.e., Punjab, Sindh, KPK, and Baluchistan. The researcher used the convenience sampling method to collect the data, but it was the consideration that the sample was selected from every province equally; in the first stage total of 36-degree awarding institutions were selected (n-32 colleges and n-4 universities). In the second stage, n-144, faculty members were chosen for data collection; participants included teaching faculty and head of department (HoD) of education, English, physics, and chemistry. Table 1 shows the sample selection procedure.

The first stage for the selection of sample institutions		
Provinces	Universities	Colleges
Panjab	1	8
Sindh	1	8
KPK	1	8
Balochistan	1	8
Total	4	32
In the second stage, faculty members were selected through convenience sampling method, including HoDs (n-4 participants from each institution)		
Faculty Members		144
Total sample		144

An open-ended questionnaire was used to collect the qualitative data, and questionnaires were distributed through google Forms and WhatsApp; in some accessible institutions, the researcher went practically and conducted the interviews recorded on questionnaires. Data

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is categorized and analyzed narratively.

Results of the Study

On the bases of interviews analyses following results were drawn;

In View point of HoDs and Faculty Members Major Issues and Challenges Facing Higher Education in Pakistan

In viewpoint of head of departments of four preprograms the following issues are facing our higher education system in Pakistan, first and foremost, higher education must be affordable. In recent years, university tuition costs have skyrocketed. Due to the rising cost, students either do not enter university or drop out later during the program. There are many ways to make Higher Education more affordable. Improving the productivity of the institution is a good area to start on. The number of students enrolled should be maxed out which will directly affect the fee structure as the cost of providing education per student will drop. Furthermore, the government needs to provide incentives and subsidies with proper accountability and transparency.

Further on, public-private partnerships should be offered to solve our higher education problems. With the stagnation of education and the privatization of institutions, access to higher education has become increasingly difficult. Through innovative partnerships with leading universities, we maximize higher education opportunities. It also ensures the success of students and staff. Similarly, these developments have the potential to transform the higher education system. Many countries have mutual partnerships with private companies.

Another area which needs improvement is Research & Development. It thrives when different groups freely discuss different perspectives. Unlike universities like Harvard and Stanford, our education system is based on a classroom approach. This traditional method of trains the student to think as the teacher is thinking, instead of self-thinking and self-assessment. There is need reform public policy that identifies the core capabilities of each school, college and university to nurture them in research and creativity in all schools, colleges and universities.

Reshaping the institutional image will also help solving issues with higher education system in Pakistan. The curriculum and theories taught in Pakistani universities have hardly been upgraded. Curriculum is rarely revised. The HEC reviews the curriculum every three years through the relevant National Curriculum Review Committees (NCRCs). However, there is a huge difference between policy making and its implementation. Therefore, incorporating innovative ideas and methods into design courses helps to stimulate students' ability to enhance their performance and abilities. Because the purpose of this study is to explore creativity and imagination of the university students so they are motivated to create work through pedagogical design.

We also need to build institutions that allow students to excel in their professional lives. In this scenario, where there is a lack of quality in the institutions, the workhorse development is a distant desire. In order to provide quality education that is in line with international standards, it is important to build training institutes. Clearly, we need Skill. So, we need to establish high quality institutions. The National University of Sciences and Technology

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(NUST), Quaid-e-Azam University, Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS) are good examples.

Fighting for equality, including the establishment of quotas in educational institutions, is a need for us. People who were not able to assist themselves for reasons that prevented them from getting a fair share in schooling include those who were discriminated against based on their gender. According to the most recent economic study conducted in Pakistan, the percentage of literate women is still lower than the percentage of literate men. In a similar vein, prejudice based on caste and religion leads to the complete exclusion of many individuals from the educational system. The government of Pakistan is dedicated to integrating them into the system. Nevertheless, we must make this a top priority.

Our educational system stuffs data, texts, and lectures into the skulls of graduating students, preparing them to enter the workforce. Which results in a mind that is whole. However, in this day and age of the Internet, it is not necessary to have a well-rounded mind. We can locate anything with only two clicks of the mouse. You really need to find someone with a fantastic intellect. A mind that can respond to unknown facts and specifics and genuinely synthesize material that has not been previously explored.

From the perspective of the person who was interviewed, the most significant obstacle is the governance of higher education at two crucial levels, namely the Higher Education Commission or commissions and the administrations of the universities themselves. When Pakistan had a single commission at the federal level, the country's publicly supported institutions had improved levels of funding, management, and organization. First the Punjab and subsequently the Sindh governments formed their own higher education commissions after the approval of the 18th constitutional amendment, which made education the exclusive responsibility of the provinces. In actuality, public universities have lost their autonomy due to the fact that they are now regulated by bureaucracy as well as political masters. This control extends from the selection of vice chancellors to the adoption of internal university rules and regulations. To a greater extent than at any previous point in Pakistan's history, politically appointed vice chancellors are now able to exert a greater level of political influence on the nation's educational institutions than ever before.

Concerning funding is a significant issue. Public universities only get roughly forty percent of their total budget, with the federal government contributing thirty-four percent and provincial governments contributing between six and eight percent. They have to generate sufficient funds to cover sixty percent of these costs via the collection of student fees. It places a greater strain on families in the middle class while simultaneously forcing the poor out of the system. One source from UNESCO reports that just 1.5 percent of people living in poverty are able to finish their education at the university level. In the current fiscal year 2022-23, it is estimated that the federal government will provide approximately PKR 30 billion for the recurrent expenses and PKR 41 billion for the development expenses for public universities. Despite this, vice chancellors have protested and continue to demand PKR 102 billion.

The higher education system is now confronted with several difficult difficulties, such as limited financing, inadequate facilities, quality and standards, a lack of academic freedom and autonomy, increased social expectations, and an increase in the demand for higher education. It should be noted that a small portion of higher education in developed countries is focused on the training of technologists through short courses. And often in Pakistan we are

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promoting traditional courses that do not create technological mindsets. In the second part of Higher Education is that students seek higher level professionalism to enhance their career.

Students want secure future regarding the employment opportunities. If we come to know that our course will support us not only in Pakistan but also in abroad then it would be meaningful course.

Management is one of the most significant contributing factors to the challenges that face higher education in Pakistan. Management has been main concern of Pakistan since independence. Even the people in charge of our government have lower levels of education, so they have no clue how to run the various systems. Since unskilled and inexperienced personnel is being recruited through sidestepping the merit system, one would wonder how an unskilled and inexperienced guy could possibly administer the system effectively.

Employment is also the most pressing concern in Pakistan, which exacerbates the country's existing challenges with regard to higher education. Students go into business without finishing their educations because they don't believe there are prospects for them to advance their careers or make high money in large corporations or government agencies since there aren't enough jobs available to them.

The professors and lecturers who work in colleges and universities have degrees, but when they first begin their careers as educators, they lack the experience and expertise necessary to accomplish their jobs effectively. Every educated kid in Pakistan would want to enter the teaching sector despite their lack of enthusiasm and experience since it is rather simple to find a job in educational institutions in Pakistan.

To begin, the duty of coming up with creative solutions to problems facing the expansion of higher education falls squarely on the shoulders of the Pakistani government. The educational process requires enough direction and monetary support. The government should establish training institutes in which teachers and academics may get training. These institutions should be accessible to trainees. Education is the single most important factor in a country's overall level of development and should thus get a sizeable portion of the budgetary resources available. Every single person ought to have the same educational opportunities. All of these were the most significant issues plaguing Pakistan's higher education system, and since we have lower standards, we cannot even compare our educational system to that of less developed nations. If we want the issues with higher education in Pakistan to be solved, we will have to take some action ourselves.

There are now 62.3 percent of people in Pakistan who can read and write. The Education Budget represents just 1.7 percent of GDP, which is the lowest percentage among the countries in the area. In the budget year 2022-23, there is provision for an expenditure of Rs 74,609 billion for tertiary education affairs and services; Rs 3,786 billion for pre-primary and basic education; Rs 8,863 billion for secondary education affairs; and Rs 2 billion for administration. Under the Public Sector Development Program (PSDP), the Higher Education Commission (HEC) would receive a total of 44,174 billion rupees in funding for the academic year 2022-23. (Business Recorder June 11, 2022).

Significant problems with the education system include inadequate budget allocation, a failure to implement policies, a flawed examination system, inadequate infrastructure at educational institutions, a shortage of qualified teachers, low student enrollment, a

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disorganized and aimless education system, a high number of students who drop out of school, increasing political interference, an outmoded educational programme, instances of corruption, ineffective management and supervision, a lack of uniformity, an absence of research, an absence of faculty development, and the cost of education.

Every country in the world has to priorities maintaining a strong educational system. Every country advances its population, also known as its human resources, by placing a significant emphasis on educational and occupational training. We have a terrible education system that lacks any clear sense of purpose, suffers from a lack of cohesiveness, and is more inclined toward providing a broad education rather than the cultivation of skilled manpower. This has led to widespread unemployment. In addition to this, it causes individuals to experience significant levels of political, social, economic, and cultural anguish. Within the current educational system, neither science nor technology are used in any way. Students are unable to acquire skills in critical thinking, creative thinking, imaginative thinking, reasoning, experimentation, innovation, and creation.

Many different political parties recruit prospective students to serve as their delegates. Several different instructors have them participate in this activity as members of the party. In return for their assistance, these teachers get favours and perks from parties in the form of assisting their pupils in obtaining admissions, the providing of question papers, and the granting of excellent scores according to a list supplied by the party.

These admission exams are being implemented with the intention of favouring the political parties' own families, relatives, acquaintances, or employees in order to build their vote bank in their respective constituencies.

The examinations are bogus, as are their results and the merit lists that are shown; all of these are phoney. Because of this, a significant number of kids who might benefit from receiving this opportunity do not have it available to them.

Students are not provided with any practical or contextual knowledge but rather simply with theoretical information. Even after earning their degrees, the majority of students do not possess the qualifications necessary for employment and are thus unable to be integrated into the labour force. Before graduating, students should be required to spend at least one semester working for recognized companies. This will allow them to get acclimated to the atmosphere of an office and familiarize them with the operations of a variety of various types of businesses. Activities, Role plays, Case Studies, Worksheets, Research Projects, Seminars, Symposiums, Lecture Series, and Events should be organized for the students with their complete and total participation. This will ensure that the students not only have ownership of the activity but also have the opportunity to meet influential people from large corporations and well-known brands.

Because the majority of institutions do not have any kind of relationship with local businesses, the students who attend such universities have difficulty getting jobs after graduation. Students should have the opportunity to learn about the ins and outs of how industries function, particularly during the student's final two semesters of schooling, from industrialists who have been invited to teach at universities. This will give students a better chance of being hired by relevant industries after graduation.

The Education Sector is not contributing in any way to the Building of the Nation. Students who go through our educational system are growing up with the mentality that the only

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nations that provide a decent education are foreign ones, and that in order to have a chance at a successful profession, they need to study abroad. Students, in general, have low levels of patriotism, civic awareness, loyalty, and affection for their country and the people who live there, and they see those people as being beneath them in comparison to the rest of the world. As a result, our crème de la crème has left the country to pursue higher education elsewhere because they are status aware and since doing so has an ostentatious impact. On the other side, students who get themselves enrolled here in Pakistan feel that it is ideal for them to transfer overseas for additional studies, job search, and professional advancement once they have already received their degrees. When they find a job there, their goal is to remain there permanently and eventually get citizenship in the host nation so that they may have dual nationality. Our most talented young people have relocated to other countries, such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Germany, Spain, Italy, Australia, Malaysia, South Africa, and the Gulf Region. They are providing their best services, earning handsome salaries, and living luxurious lifestyles in those countries, where they do not have to worry about threats to their safety such as terrorist attacks, bomb blasts, sectarian unrest, traffic congestion, pollution, smog, or energy shortages, among other things.

The nation's ongoing energy crises and load shedding have had a disastrous impact on the standard of education in the country. In the summer, when the temperature is high and the humidity is high, there is suffocation, a lack of oxygen, the stench of perspiration, and a loss of student focus in their studies in a classroom that has between 68 and 70 kids and extremely little space for the instructor to move about. The pupils and the instructors are very demotivated as a result of this, and many of them want to quit.

Male professors and students often engage in sexual harassment of female pupils and female teachers. A significant number of pupils have been warned not to speak out against the offender. At colleges, a significant number of male professors give excellent scores to female students who have been sexually assaulted. When it comes to jobs, women who are involved in illegal activities of this kind and who are involved with the management are eligible for all kinds of benefits of increments. These benefits include an increase in salaries, opportunities to take courses abroad, and promotions, and in some cases, female faculty members were awarded PhD degrees even though their research work did not meet the mark and was rejected by external supervisors.

In order to preserve the excellent educational and pedagogical standards that are now in place, parental participation is essential at every level of schooling.

Students are not being produced by the education system who are learning from education in accordance with the requirements of the standard to which they are being held while they are studying. Perhaps a student who is currently enrolled in a Ph.D. programme has the same level of expertise as the course instructor alone. This "Learning Crisis" has evolved into the most significant challenge facing our country's contemporary educational system. It indicates that there is a significant divide between the inputs and outputs of universities.

In Pakistan, students are mainly interested in pursuing careers in medicine and engineering. The majority of parents pressured their kids to choose a career in engineering or medicine as their only option for further education. They are not permitted to choose topics or themes on their own will.

Insincerity on the part of teachers was one of the most widespread challenges that most

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pupils encountered throughout their time in school. They did not educate the students the proper approach to teach, since the majority of the professors are not very experienced in their field and the students are expected to study and learn. They are wasting the pupils' time with their actions.

There is inequity amongst the pupils because of the teachers. They did not give equal weight to the contributions of all of the pupils in the class.

They skipped the class so they wouldn't have to listen to the lecture that was being given to the pupils. They did not provide a sufficient amount of time to the kids.

Conclusions

1. The curriculum and theories taught in Pakistani universities have hardly been upgraded. Curriculum is rarely revised. The HEC reviews the curriculum every three years through the relevant National Curriculum Review Committees (NCRCs).

2. In order to provide quality education that is in line with international standards, it is important to build training institutes. Clearly, we need Skill. So, we need to establish high quality institutions. The National University of Sciences and Technology (NUST), Quaid-e-Azam University, Lahore University of Management Sciences (LUMS) are good examples.

3. Our educational system stuffs data, texts, and lectures into the skulls of graduating students, preparing them to enter the workforce. Which results in a mind that is whole. However, in this day and age of the Internet, it is not necessary to have a well-rounded mind. We can locate anything with only two clicks of the mouse. You really need to find someone with a fantastic intellect.

4. When Pakistan had a single commission at the federal level, the country's publicly supported institutions had improved levels of funding, management, and organization. First the Punjab and subsequently the Sindh governments formed their own higher education commissions after the approval of the 18th constitutional amendment, which made education the exclusive responsibility of the provinces. In actuality, public universities have lost their autonomy due to the fact that they are now regulated by bureaucracy as well as political masters. This control extends from the selection of vice chancellors to the adoption of internal university rules and regulations.

5. The higher education system is now confronted with several difficult difficulties, such as limited financing, inadequate facilities, quality and standards, a lack of academic freedom and autonomy, increased social expectations, and an increase in the demand for higher education.

6. It should be noted that a small portion of higher education in developed countries is focused on the training of technologists through short courses. And often in Pakistan we are promoting traditional courses that do not create technological mindsets.

7. Management is one of the most significant contributing factors to the challenges that face higher education in Pakistan. Management has been main concern of Pakistan since independence. Even the people in charge of our government have lower levels of education, so they have no clue how to run the various systems.

8. The professors and lecturers who work in colleges and universities have degrees, but when they first begin their careers as educators, they lack the experience and expertise necessary to accomplish their jobs effectively.

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9. The government should establish training institutes in which teachers and academics may get training.
10. shortage of qualified teachers, low student enrollment, a disorganized and aimless education system, a high number of students who drop out of school, increasing political interference, an outmoded educational programme, instances of corruption,
11. These admission exams are being implemented with the intention of favouring the political parties' own families, relatives, acquaintances, or employees in order to build their vote bank in their respective constituencies.
12. The examinations are bogus, as are their results and the merit lists that are shown; all of these are phoney. Because of this, a significant number of kids who might benefit from receiving this opportunity do not have it available to them.
13. Students are not provided with any practical or contextual knowledge but rather simply with theoretical information. Even after earning their degrees, the majority of students do not possess the qualifications necessary for employment and are thus unable to be integrated into the labour force.
14. Because the majority of institutions do not have any kind of relationship with local businesses, the students who attend such universities have difficulty getting jobs after graduation.
15. The nation's ongoing energy crises and load shedding have had a disastrous impact on the standard of education in the country. In the summer, when the temperature is high and the humidity is high, there is suffocation, a lack of oxygen, the stench of perspiration, and a loss of student focus in their studies in a classroom.
16. Male professors and students often engage in sexual harassment of female pupils and female teachers. A significant number of pupils have been warned not to speak out against the offender. At colleges, a significant number of male professors give excellent scores to female students who have been sexually assaulted. When it comes to jobs, women who are involved in illegal activities.
17. There is inequity amongst the pupils because of the teachers. They did not give equal weight to the contributions of all of the pupils in the class.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that first and foremost, higher education must be affordable.
2. Public-private partnerships should be offered to solve our higher education problems.
3. Another area which needs improvement is Research & Development
4. Curriculum is rarely revised. The HEC reviews the curriculum every three years through the relevant National Curriculum Review Committees (NCRCS).
5. In order to provide quality education that is in line with international standards, it is important to build training institutes. Clearly, we need Skill.
6. First the Punjab and subsequently the Sindh governments formed their own higher education commissions after the approval of the 18th constitutional amendment, in actuality, public universities have lost their autonomy due to the fact that they are now regulated by bureaucracy as well as political masters. It should be centralized system.
7. Government should enhance the funds for HEC for lowering the fesses.

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8. It should be noted that a small portion of higher education in developed countries is focused on the training of technologists through short courses. And often in Pakistan we are promoting traditional courses that do not create technological mindsets.
9. The government should establish training institutes in which teachers and academics may get training.
10. Students are not provided with any practical or contextual knowledge but rather simply with theoretical information. It is recommended that practical knowledge should be enhances.
11. Majority of institutions do not have any kind of relationship with local businesses, the students who attend such universities have difficulty getting jobs after graduation. It is recommended that stakeholders Demand must be kept in mind.
12. The nation's ongoing energy crises and load shedding have had a disastrous impact on the standard of education in the country. It should be solved.

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